

ЖАРРОХЛИК АМАЛИЁТИДАН КЕЙИНГИ АСОРАТЛАНГАН ВА АСОРАТЛАНМАНГАН ЧУРРАЛАР.**А.А.Ражапов., Р.Х.Каримов., Ш.Э.Жумабаев. А.Ж.Бекчанов.**

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Муаммонинг долзарблиги: Умуман олганда, чурра ҳосил бўлишининг маҳаллий ва умумий сабаблари мавжуд. Маҳаллий сабабларга қорин деворидаги бўш, «нуқсонга эга бўлган жойлар» киради: киндик ҳалқаси, қорин орти чизиғи, спигел чизиғи, Пти ва Гринфельд учбурчаги чов ва сон каналлари киради. Умумий сабабларга ирсий омиллар (20-25%), беморнинг ёши (20-40 ёш орасида), жинси (80%- 90% эркаклар касалланади), спланхноптоз (ички аъзоларнинг паст жойлашиши), ориқлаб кетиш, қорин мушакларининг кучсизлиги, қорин бўшлиғи ичидаги босимнинг ошиши, сурункали йўтал, простата аденомаси, туғиш жараёни, қабзият, ич кетиш, қорин бўшлиғидаги босимни оширувчи чолғу асбобларини чалиш киради.

Ишнинг мақсади: ишнинг мақсади сифатида 2024 йил давомида РШТЎИАМ Хоразм филиалига мурожаат қилган беморларнинг анамнестик тахлили, касаллик тарихлари ўрганилди.

Материал ва усуллар: ишнинг материали сифатида 2024 йил давомида РШТЎИАМ Хоразм филиали жаррохлик бўлимига мурожаат қилиб, жаррохлик бўлимида жаррохлик амалиётдан кейинги асоратланган ва асоратланманган чурралар ташхиси билан даволанган беморлардан биопсия материаллари олиниб Хоразм вилояти патологик анатомия бюросида гистологик препаратлар тайёрланиб текширилди.

Олинган натижалар: 2024 йил давомида РШТЎИАМ Хоразм филиали жаррохлик бўлимига мурожаат қилиб, жаррохлик бўлимида жаррохлик амалиётдан кейинги асоратланган ва асоратланманган чурралар ташхиси билан даволанган жами 80 нафар беморлардан олинган биопсия материаллари текшириб кўрилганда шундан, 40 нафари аёл жинсили ва 20 нафари эркак жинсли беморлар бўлиб, тайёрланган гистологик препаратлар микроскоп остида текшириб кўрилди ва аниқ ташхис қўйилди.

Хулосалар: хулоса ўрнида шуни айтиш мумкинки, жаррохлик амалиётдан кейинги асоратланган ва асоратланманган чурралар келиб чиқиш сабабли турли хил бўлиб, чурра касаллиги ичида чов чурралари ташхиси эркакларга қараганда аёллар кўп учраган.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар:

1. Bekchanov A. J. et al. Causes of death in infants born to women affected by Covid-19 disease //American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149). – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 34-38.
2. Khasanovich K. R., Tulibaevna R. D., Ziyaevich T. H. DISTRIBUTION OF PERINATAL DISEASE IN NEWBORN CHILDREN IN KHORZAM PROVINCE BY CITY AND DISTRICT AND CAUSES OF DEATH //World Bulletin of Public Health. – 2021. – Т. 5. – С. 82-85.
3. Karimov R. X., Tursunov X. Z., Ruzmetova D. T. Modern approaches to perinatal disease in diabetes in pregnant women //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 173-179.
4. Karimov R. X., & Musaev U. M. (2023). ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH

AND COMMISSION FORENSIC EXPERTISES CONDUCTED ON LIVING PERSONS. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 1(5), 61–63. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPMHS/article/view/423>

5. Каримов Р. Х., Мусаев У. М., Рузметова Д. Т. ЯТРОГЕНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРАХ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ (По данным лет обзор) //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 10-12.

6. Каримов Р. Х. и др. ВРАЧЕБНЫЕ ОШИБКИ В ПРАКТИКЕ АКУШЕРОВ-ГИНЕКОЛОГОВ //Past and Future of Medicine: International Scientific and Practical Conference. – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 114-117.

7. Kh K. R. et al. PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPIRATORY AIRCRAFT CHANGES IN INFANTS BORN FROM MOTHERS WITH COVID-19 //JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 21-28.

8. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. CLINICAL PRACTICAL ASSESSMENT APPLICATION OF POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION AS A TEST FOR ASSESSING MICROBIOCINOSIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN //Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. – 2021. – Т. 2021. – №. 1. – С. 37-49.

9. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. OCCURRENCE OF UTERINE MYOMA IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN KHOREZM REGION //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 489-492.

10. SA M., DT R. RISK FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PRETERM PREMATURE RUPTURE OF FETAL MEMBRANES IN PREGNANT WOMEN //European Science Review. – 2018. – Т. 1.

11. Sabirjanovich Y. B. et al. ETHERIOLOGICAL FACTORS OF DEATH IN PNEUMONIAS FOUND IN NEWBORNS //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 1-4.

12. Tulibayevna R. D. Characteristics of Urogenital Tract Microbiota During Pregnancy //Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 249-254.

13. Yuldashev B. S. et al. Causes of Pneumonia In Infants Born of Mothers Infected With Covid-19 //International Journal of Integrative and Modern Medicine. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 9-16.

14. Yuldashev, B. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X. (2023). OCCURRENCE OF CLINICAL PALATE AND LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(11), 80-85.

15. Kuryazov Akbar Quranbaevich, Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich, Ruzmetova Dilfuza Tulibaevna, & Bobojanov Yoldoshboy Bakhtiyor o'g'li. (2024). PREVENTION OF PERIODONTITIS DISEASE IN MIDDLE-AGED WOMEN. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MEDICINE, SCIENCE, AND EDUCATION, 1(1), 271–274. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10599587>

16. Yuldashev, B. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X. (2023). A CASE OF LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 1(9), 547-552.

17. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., & Safarboevich, R. S. (2024). RATE OF GLAUCOMA IN PENSION AGE CITIZENS (2023 in the example of the city of Urganch). *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 2(1), 4-7.
18. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., & Safarboevich, R. S. (2024). RELATIONSHIP OF OTHER TYPES OF DISEASES WITH EYE DISEASES. *МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА*, 2(1), 29-35.
19. Quranbaevich, K. A., Khasanovich, K. R., & Tulibaevna, R. D. (2024, February). CARRIES DISEASE IN YOUNG CHILDREN. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 35-37).
20. Sabirjanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., Safarboevich, R. S., & Azamatovich, K. A. (2024). DYNAMICS OF ANTHROPOMETRIC INDICATORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ONE-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences* (2993-2149), 2(2), 560-563.
21. Sabirzhanevich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., Zhumabaevich, K. U., Farkhadovich, A. A., Azamatovich, K. A., ... & Alisherovich, K. D. (2024). PREGNANCY PLANNING FOR WOMEN WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES IN NUKUS CITY (2022-2023). *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 233-241.
22. Sabirzhanevich, Y. B., Jumabaevich, K. U., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibievna, R. D., Azamatovich, K. A., & Dilshadovich, J. D. (2024). PATHOLOGICAL OCCURRENCE AND COMPLICATIONS OF THE DIABETIC TOPIC SYNDROME IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES DISEASE WHO APPLY TO THE OUTPATIENT. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 219-227.
23. Matyakubova, S. A., & Ruzmetova, D. T. (2018). Risk factors of development of preterm premature rupture of fetal membranes in pregnant women. *European science review*, (9-10-2), 96-97.
24. Sabirzhanevich, Y. B., Jumabaevich, K. U., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibievna, R. D., & Raimberganovna, M. F. (2024, March). STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DIABETES 2 DISEASE (in the example of the city of Nukus in 2023). In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 162-165).
25. Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich, Rakhimbaev Makhmud Davlatbaevich, & Radjapov Adilbek Anvarbekovich. (2024). MORPHOLOGY AND HISTOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BRAIN TISSUE IN ACUTE INTOXICATION PSYCHOSIS. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MEDICINE, SCIENCE, AND EDUCATION*, 1(7), 49-54. Retrieved from <https://universalconference.us/universalconference/index.php/icmse/article/view/2282>
26. Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich, Musaeva Iroda Mansurbekovna, & Radjapov Adilbek Anvarbekovich. (2024). MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TWELVE FINGER ULCER DISEASE. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND SOCIAL-HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES*, 1(6), 26-31. Retrieved from <https://universalconference.us/universalconference/index.php/ICNSHS/article/view/2297>
27. Karimov , R., Musaeva I., & Radjapov , A. (2024). MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND FREQUENCY OF DUDE ULCER DISEASE IN RETIREMENT PATIENTS WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME. *FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI*, 1(2), 14-20. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/fan/article/view/6894>

28. Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich, Rakhimbaev Makhmud Davlatbaevich, & Radjapov Adilbek Anvarbekovich. (2024). MORPHOLOGY OF BRAIN TISSUE IN INTOXICATION PSYCHOSIS. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE*, 1(8), 34–40. Retrieved from <https://universalconference.us/universalconference/index.php/icms/article/view/2301>

29. Kuryazov , A., Palvanov , M., Radjapov , A., & Karimov , R. (2024). MORPHOLOGY OF THE HEART IN PATIENTS WITH TUBERCULOSIS. *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION RESEARCH CONFERENCE*, 1(6), 3–8. Retrieved from <https://universalconference.us/universalconference/index.php/isirc/article/view/2324>

30. Quryazov , A., Palvanov , M., Radjapov , A., & Karimov , R. (2024). MORPHOLOGY OF THE HEART IN DIFFERENT FORMS OF TUBERCULOSIS. *International Conference on Multidisciplinary Science*, 2(8), 26–30. Retrieved from <https://mjstjournal.com/index.php/icms/article/view/1818>

